

North American Academic
Research | Volume 5 | Issue 3 |
March 2022 | Monthly Journal by
TWASP, USA | Impact Factor:
3.75 (2021)

North American Academic Research

Monthly Journal by **The World
Association of Scientists & Professionals**
TWASP, United States

Implementing Virtual Synchronous Generators for Renewable Integration

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Accepted March 13,2022

Published March 18,2022

Copyright: © The Author(s); **Conflicts of Interest:** There are no conflicts to declare.

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Funding: None

How to cite this article: Djendo Djemble Severin, Shuai Zhikang, Wen Huang, Xia Shen (2022). Implementing Virtual Synchronous Generators for Renewable Integration. *North American Academic Research*, 5(1), 70-80. doi:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6369174>

ABSTRACT

In older centralized power systems, power is often generated by massive synchronous generators (SGs), with the grid frequency defined by the prime mover's rotational frequency. The rotor inertia attribute prevents the frequency from shifting and keeps the system stable if the load changes quickly. During transient times, the rotor kinetic energy is delivered into the grid to balance power supply between generating and load. Because of the recent high penetration of renewable energy sources, the power grid is undergoing structural changes because of more inverter-based distributed generation (RES). Because inverter-based power sources lack the inertia of classic synchronous machines (SM), a high level of inverter penetration in the grid could generate grid instability and significant voltage variations. This paper looks at the mathematical modeling and control of VSGs to replicate the inertia and damping properties of SMs.

Keywords

VSG; Topology; Smart grid; RES

1. Introduction

1.1 Research Aim

Interest in distributed energy sources has grown in recent years as renewable energy sources' penetration into the electrical power grid has increased [5]. The bulk synchronous generator dominates a traditional power system due to its rotational mass and damping, as well as its capacity to control the speed

and excitation that regulate grid frequency and reactive power flow, all of which are critical to grid dynamic performance and stability.

1.2 Overview

Oil, natural gas, and coal are the primary sources of energy on the planet. Continuous use of fossil fuels, on the other hand, is now widely recognized as unsustainable since it depletes resources and pollutes the atmosphere [1]. As a result, it is critical to seek for alternate and environmentally friendly energy sources to limit the overuse of fossil fuels. Renewable energy sources (RESs), such as solar and wind energy, are predicted to provide the greatest solutions under current economic and environmental conditions.

Because of the growing popularity of clean energy sources and the tremendous innovation in the power electronics area in recent decades, there is a continual demand for the development of power distribution systems that use renewable energy sources. The rapid expansion of capacity of inverter-based distributed generators (DGs) and the widespread use of renewable energy sources (RESs) are causing significant changes in the traditional electrical power system and network [2]. For example, by 2020, Japan plans to link 14.3 GW of solar (PV) energy systems to the grid, with the capacity increasing to 53 GW by 2030 [4]. Furthermore, for the next two decades, European countries, the United States, China, and India are seriously considering using DGs and renewable energy sources (RESs) in their power systems.

Because of the lack of inertia and damping effects, the growing penetration level of DGs/RESs has had a substantial impact on grid stability [3]. The inclusion of a few small DGs in the power network may have little impact, but a large percentage of renewable energy will have a major impact on grid stability and overall grid dynamic performance. Bus voltage spikes because of reverse power flow owing to PV generation, excess energy supply in the grid because of full generation by DGs/RESs, power fluctuations because of the variable nature of RESs, and frequency regulation degradation are examples of such effects [4].

2. Literature Review

2.1 Overview

Short-term energy storage devices, in combination with a power electronics inverter/converter with the right control mechanism, can be used to create a VSG. Figure 2-1 depicts the general architecture of VSG. A DGs/RESs unit is connected to the grid via VSG under this configuration. When there is a sudden change in load or disturbance in the system, it is anticipated to behave like a conventional synchronous generator by providing inertia and damping properties virtually and presenting the same reaction as a regular synchronous generator. The VSG control block is expected to regulate the inverter's output based on the rate of change of frequency and the difference between the reference and grid frequencies, much like the swing equation governs conventional synchronous generators.

Figure 2-1: VSG structure

2.2 IEPE Topology

Virtual Synchronous Machine (VISMA) is a VSG design created by the IEPE group [14]. The VISMA-1 design is based on the principle that a simplified model of a synchronous machine will provide the reference voltage or current from grid voltage or current. Figure 2-2 depicts a high-level overview of VISMA-1.

Figure 2-2: Model of VISMA

The VISMA model starts with real-time measurement of the grid voltage which feeds the virtual synchronous machine algorithm. The SM model produces the reference current and rotational angle and triggers the inverter switching through the hysteresis controller. Machine inertia and damping properties can be changed by changing the value of SM model parameter. To compute the reference current by the SM model [5].

Furthermore, the IEPE group also developed another method, VISMA-2 [6]. Instead of using grid voltage to feed the SM algorithm, this method uses the grid current to produce the reference voltage as an output. Also, hysteresis controller was replaced by the PWM controller to utilize the constant switching frequency, which makes it easier to choose the filter circuit. The model overview and the signal flow diagram is shown in Figure 2-3

Figure 2-3: Model of VISMA 2

3. Methodology

3.1 Overview

This part provides the basic formulation and implementation of VSG used in this research. First, a brief overview of the entire system is illustrated, and later the proposed system is described with the corresponding mathematical model for each element that emulates the virtual synchronous generator. For this study, primarily an islanded microgrid was considered, which is highly recommended for rural areas. We consider several test cases to evaluate the proposed system that uses an ideal DC battery as the voltage source. Once the basic concept of VSG is evaluated on a microgrid, it can be extended for grid interface.

3.2 System overview

The islanded microgrid and control system configuration are depicted in Figure 3-1. In this microgrid, the major source of energy is a DC voltage source, as depicted in the figure's left top corner; in actuality, this may be a solar installation or another renewable energy source that creates DC voltage. The DC supply is connected to a 60 Hz inverter, which converts the electricity to AC. To control the inverter for the desired real

and reactive power that must be provided to the load, a VSG controller is used. An LC filter connects the inverter output to the load, eliminating harmonic distortion and regulating the form of the output signal.

Figure 3-1: System overview

Figure 3-1 shows the proposed VSG control system at the bottom. Park's transformation is used to convert measured three-phase voltages and currents from the load bus from the abc system to dq values. The grid's real and reactive power are also measured, and the results are used as input signals in the P-F and Q-V droop control blocks. Droop controllers were employed to provide frequency and voltage stability in the system. The phase angle and frequency of the VSG are computed by the P-F droop controller, while the reference voltage is computed by the Q-V droop controller. The reference current for the current control block will then be determined using the synchronous algorithm. The three-phase reference voltage for the PWM is calculated by the current controller. The PWM transmits the gate pulse to the inverter using the reference voltage and angle of the VSG produced by the P-F droop controller to supply the desired real and reactive power. The LC filter merely reduces inverter output harmonics. The next sections go over the various blocks seen in Figure 3-1.

4. Results and Analysis

4.1 Results for Uncontrolled System

In controlled system, we considered an uncontrolled inverter supplying power to an islanded load. The power source for the inverter is a constant DC voltage source (860V), and PWM technique was used to regulate the inverter. There was no control mechanism to regulate the voltage, current, and frequency of the inverter. A fixed reference voltage is applied to the PWM, and loads are connected through an LC filter to

remove the PWM inverter ripple current. The AC frequency of the inverter is taken as 60Hz, and the switching frequency as 2000Hz. Since this model does not have any controller, we used resistive load only, working on real power. An overview of the model is shown in Figure 4-1.

Figure 4-1: Simulink design for uncontrolled system

4.1.1 Under Normal Condition

The purpose of this study is to investigate the uncontrolled system dynamics and to determine possible areas of improvement. The DC voltage in this design was 860V and DC current was 116A. So, the baseline reference for the total power supplied by the inverter is 100KW which is same as the overall load 100KW on the grid side. Three phase inverters were operating at 180° conduction mode. Thus, the desired line voltage is 780V (L-L) which corresponds to a (peak) phase voltage of 635V (449 V_{rms}), and the output peak current of 116A (82 A_{rms}). Simulation results for these experiments are shown in Figures 4-2.

Figure 4-2: Simulated results for uncontrolled system

The voltage, current and frequency response under the normal condition without any disturbance in the system. The figure shows sinusoidal signal of the inverter because of filtering the harmonics. The peak voltage is 625V while the peak current is 100A, indicating that there are losses in the system. These findings are confirmed in the power response, where approximately 96 KW in output power was achieved. Also, there are small amplitude oscillations in power and frequency response which may adversely affect the system stability. This phenomenon implies the importance of the frequency control; if we can control the frequency, we will be able to control the real power.

4.1.2 Under Load Variations

Next, to observe the system response under a sudden disturbance from the load side, a three-phase breaker has been switched from time $t = 0.3$ sec to $t=0.8$ sec. An additional 50KW load was switched add at time $t = 0.3$ sec, and the system went back to its original load at time $t = 0.8$ sec. The simulation results are shown below in Figure 4-3 and Figure 4-4

Figure 4-3: Simulation results with added load

Figure 4-4: Simulation results with load reduction

Both the figures show the voltage, current and frequency response when a sudden change occurred in the system. When there is a sudden increase in load (in this case 50KW), the output voltage remains unchanged since the reference was set at the desired value, however, the current reacts immediately to accommodate the change of load. When load side increased by 50KW at $t = 0.3\text{sec}$, current also increased to 150A and goes back to 100A when loads are reduced back to their original value (100KW) at $t = 0.8\text{sec}$. Figure 5.5 and 5.7

show frequency drifts due to change in load. When there is a change in the load at $t = 0.3\text{sec}$, the frequency drops precipitously but returning to the rated frequency after a short time. Likewise, when the additional load was removed at $t = 0.8\text{sec}$, there was an immediate rise in frequency which returned to the rated frequency after a short time. These variations in frequency with changes in load suggest the need for adding droop controller in the system.

5. Conclusion

Because the generated electricity from some types of DGs/RESs is unsuitable for direct grid connection, inverters must be used as an interface. Inverter-based systems without spinning inertia, on the other hand, produce severe instability. While both real and reactive loads are connected, there is no evidence of a grid supporting inverter operating satisfactorily as both grid-feeding and grid-forming inverter. Inverter load sharing is also not possible with a grid connection. With inverter-based DGs, the VSG idea arose to address these concerns. An inverter is regulated in VSG in such a way that it can efficiently replicate the behavior of a traditional synchronous generator, allowing it to take use of its benefits in stabilization and controllability.

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